

Spectrophotometric determination of low levels nickel(II) in various river water samples by simultaneous mixed-micelle mediated extraction and ternary ion association system as a prior step

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Manuscript received online 28 April 2014, revised 20 November 2014, accepted 02 December 2014

Abstract : An ternary ion association cloud point extraction (CPE) method for preconcentration of nickel(II) (Ni^{II}) has been established. This is based on the complexation of the metal ions with Acid Red 88 (AR88) as the chelating agent and sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) as the anionic auxiliary ligands at pH 4 in the presence of non-ionic surfactant of octylphenoxy polyethoxyethanol (Triton X-114), prior to their determination by spectrophotometric method. The main factors affecting CPE efficiency, such as sample pH, concentration of complexing agents, non-ionic surfactant types, non-ionic surfactant concentration (Triton X-114), electrolyte types, electrolyte concentration, temperature and incubation time were investigated. Under the optimized conditions, the detection limit (3 s, $n = 10$) of Ni^{II} was $2.7 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. The relative standard deviation for ten replicate determination of the analyte was 2.6%. A linear calibration curve in the range of $10\text{--}1000 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ with a correlation coefficient of 0.9986 ($n = 15$) was acquired. The proposed method has been applied to the determination of Ni^{II} for the water samples from the rivers located in industrial and nonindustrial areas.

Keywords : Ni^{II} , cloud point extraction, ternary ion association, spectrophotometry, water samples.

Introduction

As the rapid development of industry, more and more waste water containing hazardous heavy metals was discharged into river, which is harmful to living beings and the environment around¹. Nickel is a metal frequently used in industry and is also considered essential to plants. Its bioavailability to organisms and related biochemical process is dependent on the compounds formed by nickel and such compounds are considered carcinogenic. Inhaling vapors that contain nickel can cause asthma, bronchitis, lung cancer and other diseases related to the respiratory tract, as well as exposure to nickel can lead to skin dermatitis. The Brazilian Environmental regulation and World Health Organization (WHO) have established Ni threshold limits of 25 and $70 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, respectively, in water samples². Moreover, nickel can cause a disorder known as nickel-eczema. Other studies show a disease, characterized as occupational disease, increased in patients who consume food and beverage rich in nickel³. Approximately 10% of the overall unselected adult popu-

lation suffers from allergic contact dermatitis (ACD) caused by cutaneous exposure to nickel⁴.

However, determination of metal ions at trace level is difficult for the environmental samples, owing to trace amount of these metal ions and complex contents of the matrices. Hence, preconcentration and separation technologies have to be employed to extract analytes from the complex matrix so as to obtain suitable concentrations of the analytes for accurate determination¹. Cloud-point extraction is based on the property that a solute present in aqueous solution of non-ionic surfactant is distributed between two phases⁵. Aqueous solutions of non-ionic surfactants become turbid when they are heated above the temperature known as the cloud point. The solution is then separated into two isotropic phases, i.e. a surfactant-rich phase and a bulk aqueous phase. The hydrophobic solutes and metal ions, after the formation of sparingly water soluble complex, can be enriched into the surfactant-rich phase⁶. Recently great attention has been attracted for its great potential in separation of toxic solutes

from several matrices. Procedures for preconcentration of metal ions using CPE has been based on the extraction of these metallic substances as sparingly water-soluble chelate complexes⁵.

The cloud point extraction (CPE) technique has also been applied as a procedure for determination and removal of dyes and pigments as well as analyzing metals^{7,8}.

Spectrophotometric methods are the most commonly used techniques and continue to enjoy wide popularity. The common availability of the instrumentation, the simplicity of procedures, speed, precision and accuracy of the technique still make spectrophotometric methods attractive. Spectrophotometers offer excellent performance for a wide range of spectroscopic applications from the UV to the near IR. Because of their unique combination of outstanding sensitivity, high speed, low noise, compactness, instantaneous capture of full spectra, low cost and robustness, these detectors have revolutionized spectroscopic detection⁹.

Because of the importance of this issue, a lot of researchers have done studies regarding measuring of nickel by various methods¹⁰⁻¹⁶.

In the present work we have applied ternary ion association system for cloud point extraction by the spectrophotometric method for determination of the nickel quantities in the water samples from the rivers located in industrial and nonindustrial areas.

Experimental

Apparatus :

Absorption spectra and absorbance measurements were made by a Shimadzu UV-1800, UV-Vis spectrophotometer using 1 cm quartz cells (1.0 mL). A Metrohm digital pH meter (model 691) with a combined glass electrode was applied to measure pH values. A Hettich universal 320 centrifuge was used to hasten the phase separation.

Standard solutions and reagents :

All reagents were of analytical reagent grade and all solutions were prepared using ultra pure water. Stock standard solution of nickel at a concentration of 1000 mg L⁻¹ was prepared from NiSO₄·6H₂O (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany). A stock solution of 1.0 × 10⁻⁴ mol L⁻¹ of Acid Red 88 (Fig. 1) was prepared by dissolving 0.0043 g of the Acid Red 88 (Sigma-Aldrich, Germany) in

Fig. 1. The open molecular structure of AR88.

bidistilled water and diluting to 100 mL in a volumetric flask. More diluted solutions were prepared daily using this stock solution. A 3% (v/v) Triton X-114 (Sigma-Aldrich, Steinheim, Germany) solution was prepared by dissolving 3 mL of Triton X-114 in 100 mL double distilled water. Stock solution of KCl (1.0 × 10⁻¹ mol L⁻¹) was prepared by dissolving 0.746 g KCl in bidistilled water and diluting to 100 mL in a flask. Stock solution SDS anionic surfactant (1.0 × 10⁻³ mol L⁻¹) was prepared by dissolving 0.0288 g of this reagent (Merck) in bidistilled water and diluting to the mark in a 100 mL volumetric flask. The McIlvaine's buffer solution for pH 4 was provided by dissolving 7.71 ml of 0.2 M Na₂HPO₄ in 12.29 ml of 0.1 M citric acid¹⁷.

Procedure :

For the CPE, an aliquot of the solution containing of Ni^{II} (so that its final concentration would be in the range of 10–1000 µg L⁻¹), 1.5 mL of AR88 (1.0 × 10⁻⁴ mol L⁻¹), 1.25 mL of 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol L⁻¹ of SDS, 1.5 mL of 3% (v/v) of Triton X-114, 1.5 mL of 0.1 mol L⁻¹ of KCl and 1.5 mL of McIlvaine's buffer, pH 4.0, was transferred into a 15 mL centrifuge tubes, left for 7 min. Then the solutions were mixed and kept in a thermostatic water bath for 15 min at 50 °C. The separation into two phases was accelerated by centrifuging at 3600 rpm for 7 min. The whole system was cooled in an ice bath for 5 min in order to facilitate separation phases and the bulk aqueous phase was easily decanted. Subsequently, the surfactant-rich phase of this procedure was dissolved and diluted to 0.8 mL with the methanol and transferred into a quartz cell. The absorbance was measured at 510 nm (Fig. 2) in 1 cm cells against a reagent blank.

Analysis of water samples :

The water samples are including the ones located in industrial areas : zayande rood river, karoon river and khour musa and the one located in a nonindustrial area :

Fig. 2. The complete spectrum of the complex.

pole zohre. All the collected samples were spiked with a suitable amount of standard solution of Ni^{2+} . All the aforementioned samples were filtered through a $0.22 \mu\text{m}$ membrane to remove the suspended and floated particles.

Results and discussion

In order to study Ni^{II} ion, in the presented work, a procedure is adopted which Ni^{II} is used in the presence of AR88 as a chelating agent. The interaction between nickel and AR88⁻ led to the formation of $[\text{Ni-AR88}]^+$ cationic complex. Then, SDS⁻ was used as highly sensitive ion-pairing reagent. SDS⁻ was preferentially selected as an anionic auxiliary ligand can participate in pH-dependent interactions. The reagent not only presents a strong ion-pairing ability, which can be formed ternary ion-association system. It is found in this study that Ni^{II} at trace levels formed a complex with AR88⁻ in presence of SDS⁻ as auxiliary ligand at pH 4.0 and based on this principle

a novel micellar sensitized-analytical method for the determination of trace amounts of Ni^{II} was developed. Ni^{II} in presence of AR88⁻ and SDS⁻ produced a stable ion-pair complex (ternary ion-association system), Ni-(AR88)-SDS (Fig. 3). SDS is as the anionic surfactant, sensitizing agent and an anionic auxiliary ligand. Surfactants can interact with dye and/or the metal-dye complex as an individual molecule or aggregates. With regard to the fact that, hydrophobic ion-associated complexes could be more efficiently extracted into surfactant-rich phase than ionic ion-associated complexes, small amount of anionic surfactant (SDS) was added. The addition of sensitizing agent improves the selectivity and sensitivity of the metal determinations. Electrolyte increases the efficient extraction. After testing 3 kinds of electrolyte (KCl, NaCl, KI), KCl showed the most impact on the absorbance and extraction yield. The maximum wavelength of absorption for the resultant sample was at 510 nm. The developed method is characterized by high sensitivity, operation simplicity, and low analytical cost in wide working range. To have the maximum absorbance, it is necessary to optimize various conditions which can affect the extraction. Hence, the effects of various operating conditions have been investigated and the optimum concentrations have been established for CPE.

Effect of pH :

The complex formation of metal-chelate and its chemical stability are two significant factors for cloud point extraction. The pH, which plays a singular role on formation of the complex and stability of the complex, proved to be a main factor for cloud point extraction efficiency. Fig. 4 shows the effect of pH on the nickel extraction. It was studied in the pH range of 1–8. Since, at pH 4 there was the highest absorbance, therefore pH 4 was selected

Fig. 3. The structure of ternary ion association complex.

Fig. 4. The effect of pH on the absorbance of Ni^{II} after mixed-micelle mediated extraction.

for next experiments.

Effect of chelating reagents concentration :

As it was mentioned, adding high concentrations of AR88⁻ ion to Ni²⁺ lead to [Ni-AR88]⁺ complexation. The effect of AR88⁻ concentration on the extraction yield of Ni²⁺ was studied in the range of 0.33×10^{-5} – 1.66×10^{-5} mol L⁻¹. The effect of concentration of AR88⁻ on extraction yield is shown in Fig. 5(a). As can be seen in Fig. 5(a) the absorbance increased gradually by increasing AR88⁻ concentration up to 1×10^{-5} mol L⁻¹ and decreased slowly at higher concentrations of AR88⁻. Therefore, 1.5 mL of 1.0×10^{-4} mol L⁻¹ AR88⁻ (equivalent to a concentration of 1×10^{-5} mol L⁻¹ in final solution) was chosen as the optimal ligand concentration. Finally, in order to improve the sensitivity and selectivity as well as increasing the efficiency of CPE, initially, three surfactants such cationic cetylpyridinium chloride (CPC), *N*-cetyl-*N,N,N*-trimethyl ammonium bromide (CTAB) and anionic SDS were considered and investigated in the range

Fig. 5(a). The effect of AR88 concentration on the absorbance of Ni^{II} after mixed-micelle mediated extraction.

of 0.33×10^{-4} – 1.66×10^{-4} mol L⁻¹. The best extraction yield was obtained in presence of SDS. Therefore, to the use of SDS was decided for further studies. The effect of SDS concentration, used as sensitive improving auxiliary ligand, on the extraction yield of Ni²⁺ was studied in range of 0.33×10^{-4} – 1.66×10^{-4} mol L⁻¹. The effect of concentration of SDS as well as CPC and CTAB on extraction yield is shown in Fig. 5(b). The extraction yield gradually increased by increasing SDS concentration up to 0.83×10^{-4} mol L⁻¹, and quickly declined at higher concentrations. This is probably because of an increase in the blank absorbance and decrease the absorbance of ternary ion association. As a result, 0.83×10^{-4} mol L⁻¹ SDS solution was selected as the optimal ionic surfactant concentration. Thus, after increasing SDS, the ternary ion association complex was formed as [Ni-AR88-SDS].

Fig. 5(b). The effect of SDS concentration on the absorbance of Ni^{II} after mixed-micelle mediated extraction.

Effect of non ionic surfactants concentration :

Four nonionic surfactants containing Triton X-114, Triton X-100, Triton X-45 and Ponpe 7.5 to extract the hydrophobic Ni-complex into the surfactant rich phase were studied in the range of 0.10–0.50% (v/v). The highest extraction efficiency was acquired in presence of Triton X-114. Thus, Triton X-114 was selected for further studies. The effect of Triton X-114 concentration, was studied in the range of 0.10–0.50% (v/v) and the highest absorbance was in 0.3%. It is shown in Fig. 6. Therefore it was chosen as the optimum concentration. At lower TX-114 concentrations, the extraction yield of complex is low presumably due to the insufficiency of assemblies to entrap the ternary (hydrophobic) complex quantitatively.

Fig. 6. The effect of nonionic surfactant concentration on the absorbance of Ni^{II}.

In fact, the nonionic surfactant was used to extract the hydrophobic ternary ion association complex. The results are shown in Fig. 6.

Effect of salt concentration :

The cloud point of micellar solutions can be controlled by addition of alcohols, salts, non-ionic surfactants and some organic compounds (salting-out effects)¹⁸. It has been reported that the addition of electrolytes may accelerate the separation of the two phases of the CPE procedure¹⁹. Thus, the effect of NaCl, KCl and KI was studied in the range of $0.16 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$ to $1.70 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol L}^{-1}$. The absorbance of solution increased on increasing electrolyte concentration, but the best extraction efficiency was for KCl. Hence it was selected for this work. The various amounts of 0.1 mol L^{-1} of KCl solution were tested. The absorbance of the solution reached a maximum value at concentration of 0.01 mol L^{-1} of KCl and nearly remained constant. 0.01 mol L^{-1} KCl was selected as the optimal concentration. The results are shown in Fig. 7.

Effect of equilibration temperature and time :

To obtain simple phase separation and efficient preconcentration, it is essential to optimize the equilibration temperature and incubation time. It is favorable to use the shortest incubation time and the lowest possible equilibration temperature. The impact of the equilibration temperature was investigated by various temperatures from 20 to 70 °C. The results demonstrated which the maximum absorbance was obtained for 50 °C. The dependence of extraction efficiency upon incubation time was studied over the time period of 5–40 min. An incubation time of 15 min was adequate for the highest absor-

Fig. 7. The effect of electrolyte concentration on the absorbance of Ni^{II}.

bance. A centrifuge time of 7 min was chosen as optimal at 3500 rpm.

Analytical performance :

Under the optimal working conditions, the analytical performance of the proposed method was studied. The calibration curve was linear in the concentration range of $10\text{--}1000 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. The regression equation obtained by the least square method is $A = 3.26 \times 10^{-3} C_{\text{Ni}} + 2.15 \times 10^{-2}$ for $10\text{--}1000 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ of Ni^{II} with a correlation coefficient of 0.9986 ($n = 15$), where A is the absorbance and C_{Ni} shows the concentration of Ni^{II} in $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. The limit of detection (LOD) based on $3S_b$ was $2.7 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ and the relative standard deviation (RSD) at $350 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ was 2.6 respectively ($n = 10$).

Interference studies :

In order to investigate the selectivity of the method,

Table 1. The effect of other species on the determination of $350 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ of Ni^{II} ($n = 5$)

Foreign ions	Tolerance limit ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	Recovery (%)
Na ⁺ , F ⁻ ,	1000	96.2
NO ₃ ⁻ , Li ⁺		
Cr ²⁺ , Fe ³⁺ ,	800	98.5
Cl ⁻		
Citrate, SO ₄ ²⁻	700	99.1
MnO ₄ ²⁻ , Ca ²⁺	500	102.9
NH ₄ ⁺	250	100.8
Cd ²⁺ , Ba ²⁺	100	97.7
Bi ⁵⁺	50	101.8
Zn ²⁺ , Co ²⁺	20	103.2
Cu ²⁺ , Al ³⁺ ,	10	98.4
Pb ²⁺ , Ag ⁺		

Table 2. Determination of Ni²⁺ in water samples

Sample ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)	Ni ²⁺ added ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$)	Ni ²⁺ Found ^a (%)	Recovery (%)	RSD
River water ^b	–	82.13 \pm 0.11	–	2.4
	100	180.17 \pm 0.16	98.92	2.1
	200	288.54 \pm 0.29	102.27	3.6
River water ^c	–	79.17 \pm 0.26	–	3.1
	100	175.25 \pm 0.21	97.81	2.9
	200	270.17 \pm 0.37	96.78	3.5
River water ^d	–	68.17 \pm 0.11	–	3.7
	100	169.25 \pm 0.25	100.64	2.7
	200	272.91 \pm 0.06	101.76	2.8
River water ^e	–	8.19 \pm 0.21	–	4.1
	100	105.11 \pm 0.35	97.15	3.8
	200	212.12 \pm 0.17	101.89	2.9

^a $\bar{x} \pm ts \sqrt{n}$ at 95% confidence ($n = 5$).

^bFrom karoon river, located in a industrial area.

^cFrom zayande rood river, located in a industrial area.

^dFrom khour musa, located in a industrial area.

^eFrom pole zohre located in a nonindustrial area.

aliquot of aqueous solutions containing 350 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ Ni^{II} and various amounts of other ions was taken and the proposed procedure was followed. Ni^{II} recovery was studied in the presence of other species with tolerance limits (error < 5%). The results are observable in Table 1.

Application :

The presented procedure was applied for determination of Ni^{II} in water samples. The results are demonstrated in Table 2. Practically, this work offers the results for a contrast among quantities of Ni^{II} in the industrial and nonindustrial water samples. The percentage recovery was always higher than 96% confirming the accuracy.

Conclusion

The aim of this study is spectrophotometric determination of Ni^{II} by mixed micelle mediated extraction using ternary ion association system in various water samples. The advantages of cloud point methodology (easy, safe, rapid and inexpensive) and the use of AR88⁻ as a new ion-pairing reagent (selectivity and sensitivity) for Ni^{II} ions were utilized for determination different water samples. The proposed method is simple, rapid, reproducible and highly sensitive and can be applied for quality control of Ni²⁺ in water samples. The limit of detec-

tion of the proposed method seems to be satisfactory. Furthermore, in contrast with solvent extraction methods, it is much safer, because only a small amount of the surfactant, which has a low toxicity, is used.

Acknowledgement

The authors gratefully acknowledge the financial support of this work by Young Researchers and Elite Club, Gachsaran Branch, Islamic Azad University, Gachsaran, Iran (1392).

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